

Deep-learning-guided Particle Filter for Remaining Useful Life Estimation of Composite Materials

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*CFRP: Carbon-fiber-reinforced plastic
*PdM: Predictive maintenance

- + Material properties
- + Industrial application
- High material cost
- Low repairability

- + Prevents unexpected failures
- + Reduces operational cost
- + Efficient repair scheduling

➤ Remaining Useful Life

- CFRPs have abundant potential industrial applications owing to their various advantages.
- PdM denotes a real-time analysis to predict potential damages which may lead to failure.
- Application of PdM into CFRPs is highly required for their longevity and efficiency.

*CFRP: Carbon-fiber-reinforced plastic
*SHM: Structural health monitoring

	Self-sensing	Fiber Bragg grating	C-scan
Installation	Built-in sensor network (CFs serve as self-integrated sensors) Cost ↓	Expensive and laborious	Scanning pool and a scanner are required
Monitoring	In-situ real-time	Real-time with extra sensing devices	Schedule-based
Adaptability	No limitations	Brittle sensing device with limited to geometric shape	Frequency setting is required
Geometry	No limitations	Limited to geometric shape (sensor installment)	Plate-shaped
Sensor arrangement	Array or periphery (beneficial for large structures)	Array with numerous data channels	Limited to the scanning pool size

- **Self-sensing** is advantageous for real-time health status monitoring over other SHM/NDT technologies.

Microscopic view

Self-sensing

Macroscopic view

Electrical resistance

- Real-time measured
- Simple processing
- Fewer sensors

- Self-sensing employs the inherent electrical network consisted of carbon fibers.
- Damages in CFRPs can be electromechanically characterized by electrical resistance.

*CFRP: Carbon-fiber-reinforced plastic

CFRP specimen

Sample specification

- $[0_2/45_2/-45_2/90_2]$
- $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$

Test specification

- $S_{max} = 0.6 * UTS$
- $S_{min} = 0.1 * S_{max}$
- Loading frequency = 3 Hz

Measurement specification

- 4-probe measurement

- Repetitive operation of a system significantly influences its lifespan. → **Fatigue test**
- **Electrical resistance signal** was simultaneously measured with the test.

$[0_2/45_2/-45_2/90_2]$

$[0/\pm 45/90]_s$

Loading & unloading detection

- Overall electrical resistance increased with a decrease in number of fiber contact points and load-bearing capacity of CFRPs.

→ The electrical resistance signal can be considered as health indicator of composites.

Physics-based model

- + Solid foundation of system
- + Easy to generalize
- + Interpretable
- Sensitive to numerical instability
- Requires deep domain experts
- Vulnerable to new data

➤ Knowledge-dependent

Data-driven model

- + No priori understanding required
- + Can be improved with more data
- + Extensible to new observations
- Black boxy
- Requires large dataset

➤ Data-dependent

1. Feedforward neural network (FFNN) → Data-driven

2. Long short-term memory (LSTM) → Data-driven

3. Physics-informed neural network (PINN) → Hybrid

4. Deep-learning-guided particle filter (DLG-PF) → Hybrid ***Newly proposed!**

Performance comparison

[0₂/45₂/-45₂/90₂]

[0/±45/90]_s

- FFNN performed **3-point extrapolation** using early 20% of observation.
- The result showed **linear propagation** due to the electromechanical behavior in elastic regime.
- Results from data-driven approach **highly depend** on the input training data.

$[0_2/45_2/-45_2/90_2]$

$[0/\pm 45/90]_s$

Data to be predicted

Previous data points

- LSTM performed **3-point extrapolation** using early 20% of observed data.
- LSTM was firstly trained with the early data, then **re-trained** with simultaneously incoming data.
- **Long training time and high computational cost** are required.

$[0_2/45_2/-45_2/90_2]$

$[0/\pm 45/90]_s$

- PINN **interpolates** the early data by optimizing the pre-defined loss function and predicts the signal propagation using **extrapolation** adopting the exponential degradation model.
- The whole process requires multiple parameter input, which are highly **operator-dependent**.

- 💡 How to handle knowledge-dependent characteristic of physics-based approaches?
→ ‘What if machine learning sets the boundaries?’

Know-how: Electrical resistance increases under tensile load

*RUL: Remaining useful life

Material degradation model $z_k = e^{bx} \times z_{k-1}$

$[0_2/45_2/-45_2/90_2]$

$[0/\pm 45/90]_s$

- Particle filter estimates the propagation of the electrical resistance signal and predicts RUL using the LSTM-defined initial condition.
- DLG-PF significantly reduced computational time and RUL error compared to conventional RUL prediction approaches.

*CFRP: Carbon-fiber-reinforced polymer
*DC: Direct current

Assumptions

1. Load lost by fiber breakage will be transferred equally to all intact fibers.
2. Each fiber can be considered as a resistor; CFRPs can be approximated into DC circuit.

Stress-strain relation

$$\sigma = \underbrace{f E_f \varepsilon \left(1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{E_f \varepsilon}{\sigma_c} \right)^{m+1} \right)}_{\text{fiber}} + \underbrace{(1 - f) \sigma_y}_{\text{matrix}} \quad (1)$$

Apply (1) to circuit model

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = \frac{(1 + \alpha \varepsilon)}{1 - N_f/N} - 1 = \frac{(1 + \alpha \varepsilon)}{\exp \left[- \left(\frac{\delta_{ec}}{L_0} \right) \left(\frac{E_f \varepsilon}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \right]} - 1$$

$$i_0 = i_1 = i_2 = \dots = i_k$$

$$R_{e1} > R_{e2} = R_{e3} = \dots = R_{ek}$$

DC series circuit with
equally spaced
discrete parallel cells

*GLS: Global load sharing
*CFRP: Carbon-fiber-reinforced plastic

Case I. Employ GLS model

Self-sensing signal during fatigue test

Suggested model

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = \frac{(1 + \alpha \varepsilon)}{\exp \left[- \left(\frac{\delta_{ec}}{L_0} \right) \left(\frac{E_f \varepsilon}{\sigma_0} \right)^m \right]} - 1$$

Simplify
↓

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = \frac{(1 + \alpha t)}{\exp[-(\beta t)^m]} - 1$$

- Simplified GLS model can approximate the CFRP electromechanical behavior under fatigue.
- The exponent m and coefficients α and β can be adjusted based on observation.

Case II. Apply different equations section-by-section

Self-sensing signal during fatigue test

Suggested model

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R} = \begin{cases} a * x & (0 \leq x < 3000) \\ \exp(b_1 * (x - 3000)) + b_2 & (3000 \leq x < 4000) \\ \exp(c_1 * (x - 4000)) + c_2 & (4000 \leq x < 5000) \\ \exp(d_1 * (x - 5000)) + d_2 & (5000 \leq x < 6500) \end{cases}$$

- Data points that exhibit abrupt increases indicates severe damage occurrence.
- Based on those points, different exponential equations can be applied section-by-section.

Case III. Adopt linear threshold function

Self-sensing signal during fatigue test

Suggested model

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R} = a * x + \exp(b * u(x - 3000)) + \exp(c * u(x - 4000)) + \exp(d * u(x - 6500)) + e$$

- Linear threshold function can be applied to reduce values to be predicted.
- Each term in the model will be activated after abrupt increase by real-time monitoring.

Conclusions

- Self-sensing electrical resistance signal can act as a health indicator of composite materials.
- DLG-PF hybrid approach significantly reduced the computational cost and error compared to conventional RUL prediction tools.
- Electromechanical material degradation models were suggested.

Future Work

- Apply DLG-PF algorithm into the suggested models to precisely predict the future behavior of electrical resistance signal